

哈爾濱工程大學
HARBIN ENGINEERING UNIVERSITY

Progress of

Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics:

the Proceedings of the 2020 SPHERIC Harbin International Workshop

Harbin Engineering University

Jan. 13-16th, 2020

Harbin, China

Acknowledgement

SPHERIC Harbin 2020 has been supported by

National Natural Science Foundation of China
(NSFC)

College of Shipbuilding Engineering, Harbin
Engineering University

Heilongjiang Touyan Innovation Team
Program

About SPHERIC

SPHERIC is the international organisation representing the community of researchers and industrial users of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). The SPHERIC workshop is the only global event focusing exclusively on the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) methodology and related simulation approaches.

As a purely Lagrangian technique, SPH enables the simulation of highly distorting fluids and solids. Fields including free-surface flows, solid mechanics, multi-phase, fluid-structure interaction and astrophysics where Eulerian methods can be difficult to apply represent ideal applications of this meshless method.

The SPH method was developed to study non-axisymmetric phenomena in astrophysics in the 1970s, but its application to engineering emerged in the 1990s and early 2000s. In the past twenty years the method has developed rapidly in many fields of application from impacts and fracture to breaking waves and fluid-structure interaction.

Following the impulse generated by a collection of local initiatives in 2005 (France, UK, Italy...), a need to foster and collaborate efforts and developments was identified. Since then, the SPHERIC organisation has gone on to push the development of the method forward providing a network of researchers and industrial users around the world as a means to communicate and collaborate.

For more information about SPHERIC, please visit <http://spheric-sph.org>.

SPHERIC Harbin 2020

You are cordially invited to attend the 2020 SPHERIC Harbin International Workshop (SPHERIC Harbin 2020) to be held at Harbin Engineering University (HEU) in Harbin, China, during January, 13-16, 2020. This is the second time that the workshop is held outside of Europe following the SPHERIC Beijing Workshop.

The workshop is aimed at sharing the latest theoretical developments and practical applications of the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics method. All articles on algorithm innovation and engineering applications of SPH method are welcomed.

On behalf of the organizing team, it is our honour to warmly welcome scholars and students from all over the world to attend this workshop in Harbin, and we wish you a happy and satisfactory experience in communicating, training and studying here.

For more information about SPHERIC Harbin 2020, please visit <http://spheric.hrbeu.edu.cn/>.

About Harbin Engineering University

General Information

Harbin Engineering University (HEU) sits at the scenic Songhua River in the ice city of Harbin in Northeast China. Subordinate to the Commission of Science, Technology and Industry for National Defense, HEU is a national key university of glorious history and fine traditions. It was selected to be among the first batch of "211 Project" universities that are entitled to enjoy first priority from the state in construction and development and also one of the universities that have a Graduate School. Moreover, HEU is an important base for talent cultivation and scientific research in the fields of ship industry, marine equipment, marine engineering and nuclear application. HEU encourages students to uphold and carry forward the legacy of the older generation of revolutionaries who advocate "the military spirit" of the original Harbin Institute of Military Engineering. This spirit is condensed to the school motto "academic excellence-pursuit of truth" and forms the core school values: loyalty, fortitude, solidarity, creativity.

HEU has always attached great importance to the tradition of scientific research. The school is well-known not only for the first experimental submarine, the first hydrofoil craft, the first shipboard computer, the first swath bathymeter set and dozens of other major gap-filling scientific research breakthroughs, but also for being the best in the world with several achievements such as duplex submersible vehicles, hovercrafts and gradient velocimeters. The university maintains strong technical knowledge in the shipping, ocean and nuclear fields. Its underwater robots, shipping anti-rolling technology, integrated navigation, acoustic positioning and nuclear power simulation have occupied advanced domestic and international positions, leading HEU to become one of the main forces in the basic and applied research of China's ship science and technology. It is renowned for providing key units of the navy's advanced technical equipment and being a reliable resource for developers of high-techmarine equipment in China.

History

In 1953, the predecessor of HEU, the PLA Military Engineering Institute was established, and Senior General Chen Geng acted as the first president. Chairman Mao gave the instructions for the establishment. According to the types of the services, the Institute was subdivided into five parts: Department of Air Force Engineering, Department of Artillery Engineering, Department of Naval Force Engineering, Department of Armored Forces Engineering, and Department of Corps Engineering. In 1961, the PLA Military Engineering Institute was defined as a national key institute. In April of 1994, the school was renamed as Harbin Engineering University (HEU). In August of 1996, HEU was listed as one of the key universities being enhanced by the first batch of the '211 Project'. In 2002, the Graduate School of HEU was approved for review by the State Council. HEU Intelligent Underwater Robot Lab was listed as a National Key Lab. In 2002, the Ministry of Science and Technology and Ministry of Education approved the construction of a national University Science Park within HEU. In December of 2002, the Commission of Science Technology and Industry for National Defense and the People's Government of Heilongjiang Province signed an agreement to jointly construct this university. In 2011, HEU was listed on the Major course pioneering platform. In 2017, the shipbuilding and ocean engineering discipline was selected into the country's construction plan of world-class universities and first-class disciplines, namely the "double first-class initiative". In 2018, through the international discipline assesment, experts gave the assesment of "one of the strongest program in the world".

Committees

Scientific Committee

- Prof. Ben Rogers (University of Manchester, UK)
- Prof. Stefano Sibilla (University of Pavia, Italy)
- Dr. Alex Crespo (University of Vigo, Spain)
- Prof. David Le Touzé (Ecole Centrale de Nantes, France)
- Dr. Damien Violeau (EDF LNHE, Chatou, France)
- Dr. Nathan Quinlan (NUI Galway)
- Dr. Jean-Christophe Marongiu (ANDRITZ Hydro, France)
- Dr. Andrea Colagrossi (INSEAN, Italy)
- Dr. Xiangyu Hu (Technical University of Munich, Germany)
- Prof. Rade Vignjevic (Brunel University of London, UK)
- Dr. Antonio Souto-Iglesias (Technical University of Madrid)
- Dr. Renato Vacondio (University of Parma, Italy)
- Dr. Matthieu De Leffe (Nextflow Software, France)
- Dr. Abbas Khayyer (University of Kyoto, Japan)
- Prof. Walter Dehnen (University of Leicester, UK)
- Dr. Raj Das (RMIT University, Australia)
- Prof. Alexis Héroult (Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers, France)
- Prof. Joe Monaghan (Monash University, Australia)
- Prof. Peter Eberhard (University of Stuttgart, Germany)
- Prof. Moubin Liu (Peking University, China)
- Dr. Mehmet Yildiz (Sabanci University, Turkey)
- Dr. Alexandre Tartakovsky (Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, USA)
- Dr. Pablo Loren-Aguilar (University of Exeter, UK)
- Prof. Aman Zhang (Harbin Engineering University, China)
- Prof. Xu Fei (Northwestern Polytechnical University, China)

Organizing Committee

Chair

- Prof. A-Man Zhang (Harbin Engineering University, China)

Co-Chairs

- Prof. Decheng Wan (Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China)
- Prof. Moubin Liu (Peking University, China)
- Prof. Xiong Zhang (Tsinghua University, China)
- Prof. Hongfu Qiang (Xi'an Hi-Tech Institute, China)
- Prof. Fei Xu (Northwestern Polytechnical University, China)
- Prof. Li Zou (Dalian University of Technology, China)
- A/Prof. Furen Ming (Harbin Engineering University, China)

Preface

The Harbin Engineering University is delighted to host the 2020 SPHERIC Harbin International Workshop (or SPHERIC Harbin 2020). This is an important event of 2020 in the field of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) and related particle-based methods.

The SPH European Research Interest Community (SPHERIC) workshop is the only global event focusing exclusively on the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) methodology and related simulation approaches. It aims at encouraging and facilitating the spread of the method throughout Europe and the wider international community. The SPHERIC community plays an important role in helping the development of SPH for academia, industry and government organizations. SPH is one of the most exciting new areas in the field of computational methods and is opening up the possibility of research into fields that were beyond any modelling capability.

The SPHERIC Harbin 2020 organization committee received abstracts from China, France, Germany, UK, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, Ireland, USA, Canada, Japan and Australia, while more than 50 papers were selected to present in the SPHERIC Harbin 2020. This demonstrates just how active the field is, with works ranging from traditional hydrodynamics to solids, fluid-structure interaction, high performance computing and industrial applications.

Harbin is one of the eighth most populous Chinese cities and the largest city in the northeastern region of China. Harbin serves as a key political, economic, scientific, cultural, and communicational hub in Northeast China, as well as an important industrial base of the nation. We warmly welcome scholars and students from all over the world to attend this workshop in Harbin, and wish you a happy and satisfactory experience in communicating, training and studying here.

It is a great pleasure to welcome you to Harbin, and share a successful and enjoyable meeting with you.

Professor, Harbin Engineering University
Chair, Local Organization Committee
SPHERIC Harbin 2020

Table of Contents

SECTION 1 –INTERACTION WITH SOLIDS AND STRUCTURES

1.1	“Comparative Study on Violent Sloshing with Water Jet Flows by Using the ISPH Method”	1
	<i>Yi You, Xing Zheng, QingWei Ma</i>	
1.2	“SPH simulation of water entry for catamaran cross-section with various height of side-plate”	7
	<i>Zhang Lin, Li Xiangyang, Yang Yifan, Zhang Tao†</i>	
1.3	“Research on Water Entry of Trimaran Based on SPH Multiphase Flow”	15
	<i>Yang Yifan, You Mo, Zhang Lin, Zhang Tao†</i>	
1.4	“On the importance of accurately resolving negative pressures in SPH simulations of FSI problems”	23
	<i>Peng-Nan Sun, David Le Touz’e, Guillaume Oger, A-Man Zhang</i>	

SECTION 2 –CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY

2.1	“On the numerical solution to the truncated discrete SPH formulation of the hydrostatic problem”	31
	<i>P.E. Merino-Alonso, F. Maci`a, A. Souto-Iglesias</i>	
2.2	“A new SPH-based interpolation method”	39
	<i>Kun SHI, Jianguo WEI, Qingzhi HOU, Arris S. Tijsseling</i>	
2.3	“Formulation for an angular momentum conservative SPH bulk viscosity term”	47
	<i>J. Bonet Avalos, A. Colagrossi, M. Antuono, A. Souto-Iglesias</i>	
2.4	“ δ -SPH model for multi-phase flow: how to correctly select the sound speeds of the different phases”	55
	<i>A. Colagrossi, S. Marrone, I. Hammani, G. Oger, D. Le Touze</i>	

SECTION 3 –MULTIPHASE FLOWS AND MULTIPLE CONTINUA

3.1	“Modeling Multiphase Flow Based on Axisymmetric SPH”	63
	<i>Ming-Kang Li, A-Man Zhang, Fu-Ren Ming</i>	
3.2	“SPH Modeling of Supercooled Large Droplets Impacting Hydrophobic Surfaces”	71
	<i>Xiangda Cui and Wagdi G. Habashi</i>	
3.3	“Appearance of interfacial instability using SPH and measures of mixing between phases”	79
	<i>Georgina Reece, Benedict D. Rogers, Steven Lind and Georgios Fourtakas</i>	
3.4	“A simple and accurate WENO reconstruction in SPH for compressible flows”	85
	<i>Ping-Ping Wang, Zi-Fei Meng, A-Man Zhang</i>	

SECTION 4 –APPLICATIONS: INDUSTRY

4.1	“DualSPHysics: an open-source code for engineering purposes”	91
	<i>B.D. Rogers†1, G. Fourtakas1, P.K. Stansby1, J.M. Domnguez2, A.J.C. Crespo2, M. Gmez-Gesteira2, O. Garca-Feal2, J. Gonzlez-Cao2, R. Canelas3, R. Vacondio4, C. Altomare5, and A. Tafuni6</i>	

4.2 “Study on wave-induced kinematic responses and flexures of ice floe by Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics”	98
<i>Zhang Ning Bo, Xing Zheng, QingWei Ma</i>	
4.3 “Investigation on water entry of ship sections based on SPH method”	105
<i>Han Cheng, Fu-Ren Ming, A-Man Zhang</i>	
4.4 “Simulations of helicopter ditching using Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics”	111
<i>G. Oger, A. Vergnaud, B. Bouscasse, J. Ohana, D. Le Touzé M. De Leffe, A. Bannier, L. Chiron Y. Jus, M.Garnier</i>	

SECTION 5 –BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

5.1 “Investigation of the Solid Boundary Conditions for Complex Geometries”	118
<i>Jinxuan Wang, Xiaohu Guob, Xiufang Feng</i>	
5.2 “Partial Slip Boundary Conditions in SPH”	125
<i>Aaron English, Prof. Peter Stansby, Dr. Steven Lind</i>	
5.3 “MPM Simulation of Wave Interaction with a Porous Wall”	132
<i>Lucy Harris, Dongfang Liang, Xuanyu Zhao</i>	
5.4 “Incompressible SPH Simulation of Solitary Wave Propagation on Permeable Beaches”	140
<i>Chiaki Tsurudome, Dongfang Liang, Yuma Shimizu, Abbas Khayyer, Hitoshi Gotoh</i>	

SECTION 6 –FLUID INTERACTION WITH OTHER MATERIALS

6.1 “Study on the Hull Capsizing Induced by Large-Scale Rising Bubble in SPH method”	147
<i>Xiangli Fang, Pingping Wang, Furen Ming, A-Man Zhang</i>	
6.2 “Simulation of coastal pollutant transport using smooth particle hydrodynamics”	155
<i>Wanying LIU, Qingzhi HOU*, Jianwu DANG</i>	
6.3 “Numerical simulations of three-dimensional violent sloshing flows in tanks”	163
<i>Fengze Xie, Decheng Wan</i>	
6.4 “ISPH simulation of Solitary wave propagating with $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model”	172
<i>Dong Wang</i>	

SECTION 7–MULTIPHASE FLOWS AND MULTIPLE CONTINUA

7.1 “An improved continuum surface force model for free surface flows in smoothed particle hydrodynamics”	180
<i>Wenbin Liu, Nansheng, Dongjun Ma, Mingyu, Zhang, Pei Wang</i>	
7.2 “An accurate shock-capturing SPH scheme based on Roe’s approximate Riemann solver”	188
<i>Zi-Fei Meng Ping-Ping Wang A-Man Zhang</i>	
7.3 “Multiphase MPS method for solitary wave breaking in stratified flows”	194
<i>Xiao Wen, Decheng Wan</i>	
7.4 “Towards the modelling of underwater-explosion/cavitation bubbles: proposal of a compressible multiphase SPH model”	202

David Le Touz'e, Peng-Nan Sun, Guillaume Oger, A-Man Zhang.....

SECTION 8 –MULTI-RESOLUTION OR HIGH-ORDER PARTICLE METHODS

8.1 “A multi-resolution smoothed particle hydrodynamics method for FSI”	210
<i>Chi Zhang, Massoud Rezavand and Xiangyu Hu</i>	
8.2 “Smoothed particle hydrodynamics with adaptive spatial resolution (SPH-ASR) for multiphase flows”	218
<i>Xiufeng Yang, Song-Charng Kong</i>	
8.3 “Towards high-order SPH: corrections and convergence”	222
<i>A. M. A. Nasar, G. Fourtakas, S. J. Lind, J. R. C. King, B. D. Rogers, P. K. Stansby</i>	
8.4 “Improved Multi-resolution MPS Method for Fluid-solid Interaction Problem”	228
<i>Yijie Sun, Kai Zhang, Guang Xi, Zhongguo Sun*</i>	

SECTION 9 –COUPLING TO OTHER METHODS

9.1 “Numerical simulations of liquid sloshing with elastic baffles using an element-particle coupling approach”	236
<i>Zhilang Zhang, Ting Long, Moubin Liu</i>	
9.2 “MPSFEM-SJTU solver for dam-break flows interaction with elastic columns”	241
<i>Guanyu Zhang, Decheng Wan*</i>	
9.3 “Numerical simulations of an elastic plate entry water by coupled MPS-FEM method”	249
<i>Yihao Lu, Guanyu Zhang, Decheng Wan</i>	

SECTION 10 –MULTIPHASE FLOWS AND MULTIPLE CONTINUA

10.1 “Simulation of sediment and waves motion caused by dam break based on two-phase SPH model”	257
<i>X. J. Ma†, B.W. Zhang, M. Wang, G. Y. Li, F. Song</i>	
10.2 “Numerical simulation of Laser Spot Welding using smoothed particle hydrodynamics method”	264
<i>Pengying Yang^{1,2}, Zekun Wang^{1,2}, Zhilang Zhang^{1,2}, Moubin Liu^{1,2*}</i>	
10.3 “Numerical Simulation of Dam-break Flow Based on Gas-water SPH Method”	269
<i>Zheng Wengang, Wang Yuan, , Gu Shenglong</i>	
10.4 “Analysis of Movement Characteristics of LSP in Pneumatic Conveying Pipe”	281
<i>Zhan Wang¹ Mamtimin Geni^{1,2} Xianwei Xia¹</i>	

SECTION 11 –INCOMPRESSIBLE / WEAKLY COMPRESSIBLE FLOWS

11.1 “Numerical Simulation of River Pollution Dispersion Using Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics method”	286
<i>Lirong Tian,Renzu Ga,Wengang Zheng</i>	
11.2“Consistent Particle Method simulation of sloshing problems”	294
<i>Yaru Ren, Min Luo, Pengzhi Lin</i>	

11.3 “Weakly Compressible SPH For Free Surface flow”	300
<i>Mingyu Zhang</i>	

11.4 “Research on the Protective Characteristics of Explosive Reactive Armor Based on the SPH”	303
<i>Wenhua CHU, Chunqing Yin, Haoran Li, Xuchang YE</i>	

SECTION 12 –COUPLING TO OTHER METHODS

12.1 “Application of a Coupled SPH-FEM model to the wave-submerged horizontal plate interaction”	308
<i>Ming He, Wanhai Xu, Xifeng Gao*, Bing Ren</i>	

12.2 “High speed water impacts of at plates solved by a SPH-FV Coupled approach”	316
<i>S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, A. Di Mascio, L. Chiron, D. Le Touz’e</i>	

12.3 “Coupling of SPH and FVM for two-phase flow”	324
<i>Gang Yang†1, Yi Xiang Xu1</i>	

SECTION 13 –MULTIPHASE FLOWS AND MULTIPLE CONTINUA

13.1 “Study on Light Soft Particle Suspension Velocity and Flow Characteristics”	329
<i>Orkin Rahim1,2 Mamtimin Geni1,2 Gulbahar Tohti1</i>	

13.2 “Cavitation characteristics near plate subjected to near-field underwater explosion”	335
<i>Wang Longkan, Zhang Zhifan</i>	

13.3 “A Lagrangian particle method based on GSM gradient operator and its application to droplet dynamics”	338
<i>Xiangwei Dong, Zirui Mao, G.R. Liu</i>	

SECTION 14 –CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY

14.1 “Further improvements of the δ -LES-SPH model”	344
<i>M. Antuono, D.D. Meringolo, S. Marrone, A. Di Mascio, A. Colagrossi</i>	

14.2 “Improved density diffusion term for long duration wave propagation”	351
<i>G. Fourtakas, R. Vacondio, J.M. Domínguez B.D. Rogers</i>	

14.3 “Investigations on the smoothed dissipative particle dynamics (SDPD)”	358
<i>Chao Li, Hantao Liu, Jianzhong Chang, Moubin Liu*</i>	

List of Participants	363
----------------------------	-----

δ -SPH model for multi-phase flow: how to correctly select the sound speeds of the different phases.

A. Colagrossi^{1,2}, S. Marrone¹

1) CNR-INM (INstitute of Marine engineering) Rome, Italy

2) College of Shipbuilding Engineering,
Harbin Engineering University, Harbin, China

I. Hammani³, G. Oger³, D. Le Touzé³

3) Ecole Centrale de Nantes

LHEEA research dept. (ECN and CNRS)
Nantes, France

Abstract—In the present work the multi-phase SPH model presented in Grenier et al (2019) [9] is considered and extended in order to include a diffusive term in the continuity equation. The latter based on the δ -SPH model of Antuono et al. (2012) [1], allows to improve the evaluation of the pressure field, removing numerical noise and improving also the particles spatial distribution. Beside the δ -SPH model, also the Riemann-SPH version is considered, indeed both these models can handle multi-phase flow in presence of a free-surface.

The time stepping and the choice of the speeds of sound for the different phases are discussed, showing that this choice is driven not only by physical consideration but also by numerical constraints linked to the stability of the scheme.

In this work we show that the two SPH variants, δ - and Riemann- SPH, have different regions of stability when a multi-phase flow is considered. It is interesting that for some density and speed of sound ratios the δ -SPH model allows for bigger time steps, but in other conditions it is the Riemann-SPH model to be more convenient. This is just a preliminary study on the stability constraints linked to multi-phase flow solved by SPH models. The topic deserves a further investigation in order to analyse theoretically the stability limits and derive possible solutions to go beyond the intrinsic stability boundaries of a specific SPH model.

In the last section the simulation of a water-entry problem with air entrainment is presented in order to show how the proposed SPH method is able to treat such kind of violent multi-phase flows.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-phase flows can be very important for many engineering applications (mixing/separation devices, engines, propellers, etc.). The problem of simulating multi-phase flows has been the subject of many researches in the recent years due to the growing industrial demands, in the maritime, coastal and aeronautical engineering sectors. For the simulation of these flows, a multi-phase solver is required. However, because of the complex interfaces dynamics between the phases and of the numerical constraints, the derivation of robust models is not straightforward. In this context, the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics method has proven to be a powerful method. Indeed, unlike standard mesh-based methods in SPH the fluid elementary volumes are followed in their Lagrangian motion. Therefore, the interface between two fluids will not be diffused and will remain sharply described, and no treatment is required to track them.

The present article revolves around the improvement of the multi-phase SPH formulations by Grenier et al. (2009, 2013) [9, 10]. The SPH model is compared with the Riemann-SPH by Leduc et al. (2010) [15] which presents similar characteristics, indeed both the model are suitable for simulating both interfacial and multiphase flows. Regarding the Grenier et al. formulation, modifications have been made mainly in order to produce high quality pressure fields via the adaptation of a diffusive operator added in the continuity equation.

In 2003 Colagrossi and Landrini [6] derived the first SPH multi-phase model able to treat density discontinuities with high density ratio in the fluid domain. In order to remove non-physical high-frequencies from the pressure field, they used a periodic density filtering which, however, introduced numerical instabilities close to the free-surface for long time simulations.

Español and Revenga [7] (2003) presented an SPH-DPD scheme where the particle volumes are evaluated through kernel summation; these volumes were called *thermodynamic volumes*, being non-coincident with the geometric ones. This approach was used by Hu and Adams (2006) [12] for another multi-phase SPH model. Conversely to [6], in the latter the density field is directly evaluated through the ratio between the particle masses and their thermodynamic volumes without the use of a continuity equation integrated in time. However, this SPH model cannot be used if a free-surface is present since the thermodynamic volumes cannot be evaluated in its proximity because of the truncation of the kernel support. To circumvent this issue, Grenier et al. (2009) [9, 10] proposed a multiphase model for interfacial and free-surface flows. They used a Volumetric Strain Rate equation for the time evolution of thermodynamic volumes, while the density field was evaluated by a Shepard correction.

The use of the Shepard kernel for the density field in [9, 10] is, however, not sufficient to completely eliminate the high frequency instabilities of the pressure field. In order to improve that model, in the present work we propose the use of the diffusive term introduced in the δ -SPH scheme by [1]. Since in [9] the continuity equation is expressed for the thermodynamic volumes, the diffusive term has to be modeled in a different way with respect to [1].

II. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In the present work we consider a domain Ω where different fluids or phases are present. The domain is confined by solid boundary Ω_B and also by a free-surface Ω_F . The solid boundary consists of an external frontier which contains Ω and also by solid bodies which can be inside the fluid domain and which can move across Ω_F .

The flow evolution is governed by the compressible Navier-Stokes Equation (NSE):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u}, & \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \frac{\operatorname{div} \mathbf{V}}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \\ \frac{De}{Dt} = -p \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u} + \frac{\mathbf{V} : \mathbf{D}}{\rho}, & \frac{D\mathbf{r}}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}, \quad p = f(\rho), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{u}$ is the flow velocity, $\mathbf{r}$ the position of the material points, p is the fluid pressure, ρ the fluid density, e the specific internal energy, $\mathbf{V}$ the viscous stress tensor, $\mathbf{D}$ the rate of strain tensor, $\mathbf{g}$ is a generic specific body force.

Phase changes are not considered and we assume that all the fluids can be considered barotropic, hence, the pressure is linked only with the density field, ignoring the pressure dependency on the entropy. This condition is verified since in this work we are focused on flow with limited compressibility. Thermal conductivity is neglected as well and only immiscible fluids are considered. Also the viscous and surface-tension models are not considered since the main interest is on free-surface flows and on water impacts with air-entrainment phenomena. Being the flow simulated inviscid, the numerical schemes need to be stabilized as discussed in the next section.

Regarding the inclusion of viscous and surface-tension SPH models, similarly to what shown in [9] and in [10], they can be included in the present method without any restriction.

III. MULTI-PHASE SPH MODELS

In the present section an extension of the δ -SPH model to multi-phase flow is derived considering the multi-phase SPH model of Grenier *et al.* (2009) [9]. This model is based on the use of equations for the particle volumes evolution so as to be able to treat problems involving discontinuity of the density field.

In the formulations presented in this section, similarly to the standard SPH model, the mass of the generic i -th particle, m_i , is evaluated by the initial condition at time $t = 0$:

$$m_i = \rho_{i0} V_{i0}, \quad (2)$$

where ρ_{i0} is the initial density evaluated through the pressure field and the equation of state of the specific fluid whereas the particle volumes V_{i0} are known from the particles positions inside the fluid domain at the initial time. Usually at $t = 0$ the particles are regularly positioned in the domain. Therefore, at least at the initial instant, the particle volumes coincide with the geometrical ones, and can be initialized as such. One can use also the particle packing technique described in [5]; in that case the volume can be assigned by the obtained tessellation. Differently from the densities and volumes of

the particles, the masses m_i remain constant during the time evolution guaranteeing the conservation of the total mass.

A. Derivation from Grenier *et al.* 2009

In Grenier *et al.* (2009) [9] the continuity equation is expressed through the Volumetric Strain Rate equation:

$$\frac{DV}{Dt} = V \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}), \quad (3)$$

where V is the infinitesimal volume associated to the material point which move with the flow velocity $\mathbf{u}$ and D/Dt is the Lagrangian derivative.

Similarly to the SPH model presented in Colagrossi & Landrini (2003) [6] the use of the continuity equation allows to simulate flow in presence of a free surface as originally described by Monaghan (1994) [19]. This is not the case when adopting the direct evaluation of the volume or the density from the particle positions as in [12].

As usually performed in the SPH framework, the divergence operator can be approximated as:

$$\langle \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j. \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_i$ and $\mathbf{u}_j$ are the flow velocity associated with the generic particles i and j , ∇W_{ij} is the spatial derivative of kernel function, with respect the position of particle i , and V_j the volume of the j -th particle. The kernel function W_{ij} adopted in this work is the C2 Wendland function defined in [28]. The support of its domain is equal to $2h$, where h is the noted as *smoothing length*. The W_{ij} is a function of the relative distance between particle i -th and j -th, i.e. $W_{ij} = W(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|; h)$.

From the above equations, the time evolution for the particle volumes can be derived as:

$$\frac{dV_i}{dt} = V_i \langle \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i. \quad (5)$$

In order to integrate in time eq. (5) the initial particles volumes V_{i0} have to be initialized as described in the previous section. From these volumes also the radius of the particles Δx_i can be derived and the ratio $h/\Delta x_i$ is set equal to 2 (i.e. about fifty particles are present in the support of the kernel function W in a 2D framework).

The Grenier *et al.* (2009) [9] model differs from other SPH models where a continuity equation is written in terms of density. Indeed, similarly to Espanol *et al.* (2003) [7], the particles volumes are evaluated before the density. It follows that the particles densities can be calculated directly through the ratio:

$$\rho_i(t) = m_i / V_i(t), \quad (6)$$

or through an interpolation formula. For example, in Grenier *et al.* (2009) [9], after the time integration of eq. (5), a Shepard interpolation of the particles masses is used to evaluate the density field:

$$\rho_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{X}} m_j W_{ij}^S; \quad W_{ij}^S := \frac{W_{ij}}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{X}} W_{ik} V_k}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{X}, \quad (7)$$

where χ indicates a generic fluid in the domain Ω (*i.e.* the above summations are computed only using particles belonging to the same phase). The function W_{ij}^S is known in the literature as Shepard kernel and it satisfies by construction the normalization property (for more details see *e.g.* [8]). Thanks to this relation the density discontinuities can be treated explicitly since, conversely to the kernel W_{ij} , the summation of the Shepard kernel is not affected by the truncation of the kernel support. On the other hand, it is worth to note that the Shepard kernel W^S requires the a priori knowledge of the particles volumes V_k in eq. (7).

Once the density field is evaluated, the pressure is obtained through the use of a stiff equation of state:

$$p_i = f_\chi(\rho_i) = \frac{\rho_{0\chi} c_{0\chi}^2}{\gamma_\chi} \left[\left(\frac{\rho_i}{\rho_{0\chi}} \right)^{\gamma_\chi} - 1 \right] + p_b, \quad \forall i \in \chi \quad (8)$$

where γ_χ is the polytropic coefficient of phase χ , p_b is a background pressure constant in all the fluid domain and $c_{0\chi}$ is the speed of sound of the phase χ . Concerning the choice of speed of sound, section IV has been devoted to this topic. Indeed, beside physical aspects we show that also stability constrains are linked to this choice. It is worth to stress that state equation (8) is adopted for both gas and liquid phases, as the latter are treated as weakly-compressible media.

Following the work of Colagrossi *et al.* (2009) [4], using a variational principle on the energy equation of the flow, the smoothed divergence operator defined by eq. (4) leads to the following smoothed pressure gradient:

$$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i = \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla W_{ij} V_j. \quad (9)$$

The scheme proposed by Grenier *et al.* (2009) [9] is able to treat interfacial flows in the presence of a free-surface. However, as other weakly-compressible SPH schemes, it presents numerically high frequency oscillations on the pressure field. In order to remove the genesis of these spurious acoustic waves the δ -SPH model by Antuono *et al.* (2012) [1] can be adopted. The latter consists in adding a diffusive term in the continuity equation which is able to filter high-frequency numerical pressure noise. The pressure signals which are characterized by wave numbers with wave length smaller than the SPH kernel support are dissipated thanks to the use of this diffusive term.

B. The δ -SPH model

The equation of the δ -SPH in the context of the multi-fluid flow, written for a generic i^{th} particle of generic phase χ , reads

as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dV_i}{dt} = V_i \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \delta h c_{0\chi} \sum_{j \in \chi} \mathcal{D}_{ij}^V \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} = - \sum_j (p_j + p_i) \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \rho_i \mathbf{f}_i + \alpha h c_{0\chi} \rho_{0\chi i} \sum_{j \in \chi} \pi_{ij} \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i, \quad \rho_i = \sum_{j \in \chi} m_j W_{ij}^S, \quad p_i = f_\chi(\rho_i) \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

where c_0 is the artificial speed of sound, ρ_0 the density of the fluid at rest condition, and α and δ the two parameters for the artificial viscous terms. The δ parameter is always set equal to 0.1, while α ranges between 0.01 up to 0.1 depending by the problem at hand. For example for impulsive and violent impact problems $\alpha = \mathcal{O}(0.1)$ is generally adopted in order to stabilize the scheme. Regarding the particle interaction terms $\mathcal{D}_{ij}^V$ and π_{ij} of the diffusive terms, they are defined as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{D}_{ij}^V := V_i \left[2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_j}{\rho_i} \right) - \frac{1}{\rho_i} (\nabla^L \rho_i + \nabla^L \rho_j) \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ij} \right] \frac{\mathbf{r}_{ij}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij}|^2}, \\ \pi_{ij} := \frac{\mathbf{u}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ij}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij}|^2}, \end{array} \right. \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_{ij} := (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j)$, $\mathbf{u}_{ij} := (\mathbf{u}_i - \mathbf{u}_j)$ and $\nabla^L \rho$ is the renormalized density gradient defined as:

$$\nabla^L \rho_i := \sum_j (\rho_j - \rho_i) \mathbb{L}_i \nabla W_{ij} V_j, \quad \mathbb{L}_i^{-1} := \left[- \sum_j \mathbf{r}_{ij} \otimes \nabla W_{ij} V_j \right] \quad (12)$$

(for more details see [2]). Since the present method is based on a continuity equation for the particle volumes (see eq. (5)), the diffusion term proposed in [1] has been rearranged. Indeed, even if it is added in the continuity equation written for the particles volumes the diffusive term is still depending on the density variations.

The parameters δ is always set to 0.1 independently of the simulation, and in the case of viscous flow the α -term is replaced by the real one, same as in single-phase δ -SPH [16]. Note that the sums in the diffusive terms, as well in the density one, are made only over particles of the same phase as particle i . This is motivated by the fact that we do not want to alter the explicit treatment of the interface discontinuities by allowing a diffusion mechanism across the different phases. However, such a choice can lead to numerical instabilities needing the addition of a numerical surface tension, as explained in the following subsection.

1) *Artificial surface-tension model:* Similarly to what already underlined by Grenier *et al.* (2009) [9], when using the models presented above to simulate multi-phase flows where surface tension effects are negligible, a non-physical

inter-penetration of particles belonging to different phases may occur, leading to a numerical fragmentation of the fluid interfaces. In order to prevent this, a small repulsive force has been introduced in [9] modifying the pressure gradient as:

$$\nabla p_i = \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \epsilon_\chi \sum_{j \in \bar{\chi}} (|p_i| + |p_j|) \nabla W_{ij} V_j \quad (13)$$

where ϵ_χ is a parameter ranging between 0.01 and 0.1. The second summation applies to particles that do not belong to the fluid of the i -th particle. This set of particle is noted by $\bar{\chi}$. The above choice naturally implies that on the free-surface the artificial pressure term of eq. (13) is null.

As shown in [6], the last term of eq. (13) models a cohesion force, *i.e.* a surface tension, as also explained in [21].

In Szewc et al. (2015) [25] it is shown in an heuristic way how the spurious interface fragmentation in multiphase SPH can be controlled by the coefficient ϵ_χ . However, it needs to be increased with a factor $1/h$ when increasing the spatial resolutions in order to maintain the effect of the second term of eq. (13).

C. Multi-fluid Riemann-SPH scheme

Vila [27] and Parshikov et al. [24] proposed to stabilize the SPH standard scheme by solving Riemann problems at each pair interaction as in the Finite Volume Method.

The Riemann problem is solved at the interface between particles i and j located at $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{x}_j}{2}$, with an interface velocity $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{u}_j}{2}$ and a normal direction $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_{ij} = \frac{\nabla_i W_{ij}}{\|\nabla_i W_{ij}\|}$. The Riemann-SPH scheme proposed by Vila reads:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i \\ \frac{dV_i}{dt} = V_i \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d(\rho_i V_i)}{dt} = -V_i \sum_j 2\rho_E (\mathbf{u}_E - \mathbf{u}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{ij})) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d(\rho_i V_i \mathbf{u}_i)}{dt} = \rho_i V_i \mathbf{g} - V_i \sum_j 2(\rho_E \mathbf{u}_E \otimes (\mathbf{u}_E - \mathbf{u}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{ij})) + p_E \mathbb{I}) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where ρ_E , $\mathbf{u}_E$ and p_E are the Riemann problem solution between particles i and j . These solutions can be computed via exact [13] or linearized [20, 23] solvers. The MUSCL (Monotonic Upstream Scheme for Conservation Laws) method proposed by Van Leer [26] is used to lower the numerical dissipation while increasing the scheme to the second order. It consists in replacing the left and right states by piecewise linear reconstructions.

This Riemann-SPH scheme can be adapted to take into account multiphase flows by blocking mass fluxes between the particles, *i.e.* the interface velocity of the Riemann problem equal to the solution of the Riemann problem, *i.e.*:

$$\mathbf{u}_E = \mathbf{u}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{ij}) \quad (15)$$

(see for details [15]).

IV. TIME STEPPING, CHOICE OF THE SOUND SPEEDS AND NUMERICAL STABILITY CONSTRAINTS

A fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme is used to march in time the systems of equations (10). As described in [1], in order to reduce CPU costs and improve the stability of the scheme, the diffusive δ -term is updated outside the sub-time steps of the Runge-Kutta scheme while it is “frozen” inside.

The time step of the simulations is set as:

$$\Delta t = \min_i (\Delta t_i^c), \quad \Delta t_i^c = K \frac{2h}{c_{0\chi}} \quad \forall i \in \chi \quad (16)$$

where Δt_{ci} is the time step due to the acoustic constraints, K is the CFL factor, and $2h$ is the support of the C2 Wendland kernel (see *e.g.* [1]). The time step Δt_{ci} depends on the specific speed of sound of each phase χ . The K factor is set smaller than the maximum value K_{max} which depend on the specific time scheme, the chosen kernel function and it can be also problem dependent. In our cases, K is set equal to 0.75 in a heuristical way, indeed with such a value the scheme has been found to be always stable even for violent flow conditions.

As stated in section I, this work focuses on interfacial flows in the presence of a free-surface. More specifically, problems where a liquid $\mathbf{X}$ interacts with a gas pocket $\mathbf{Y}$ and a free-surface $\mathbf{FS}$. The gas pocket $\mathbf{Y}$ in some conditions can be compressed by the liquid phase (for example when considering water-entry problems where air entrainment is relevant). The compressibility of the gas is linked to its speed of sound c_{0Y} which cannot be chosen for computational convenience but has to be equal to the real one. In general, for cases where the compressibility is important for the gas pockets dynamics, the Euler non-dimensional number should be preserved in the simulation. The latter is defined as:

$$Eu := \frac{P_{0Y}}{\rho_X U_X^2}, \quad P_{0Y} := \frac{\rho_{0Y} c_{0Y}^2}{\gamma_Y}$$

where P_{0Y} is the pressure of the gas pocket in rest condition and U_X is the speed of the liquid acting against the gas pocket.

Conversely the liquid phase $\mathbf{X}$ is treated as a weakly-compressible medium, *i.e.* for computational convenience the speed of sound can be reduced with respect to the real one up to the limit:

$$c_{0X} \geq 10 \max \left(U_{max}, \sqrt{\frac{\Delta p_{max}}{\rho_{0X}}} \right) \quad (17)$$

where U_{max} and Δp_{max} are the maximum expected velocity and pressure variation in the phase $\mathbf{X}$. The condition (17) guarantees the weakly-compressible regime, that is, fluid density variations for $\mathbf{X}$ shall remain smaller than 1% (see *e.g.* [17]). This allows the adoption of a lower value of the sound speed with respect to the the actual value which would lead to very small time steps and, therefore, high computational costs.

The above conditions where c_{0Y} is the real one and c_{0X} is a reduced speed of sound for the liquid, can lead to the counter-intuitive situations in which the air phase is modelled using a speed of sound larger than the liquid one. However, as explained in [6], [9] and shown in section V the above choice remains a good approximation provided that the constraint (17) is respected.

In Colagrossi & Landrini (2003) [6] a further constraint, this time on the ratio between the speeds of sound c_{0X} and c_{0Y} , is included and reads as:

$$P_{0Y} = P_{0X} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{c_{0X}}{c_{0Y}} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_X \rho_{0Y}}{\gamma_Y \rho_{0X}}} \quad (18)$$

The nature of this constraint was not justified by [6]. In this work we show that it is linked to a stability constraint of the scheme and can be rewritten in a more complete fashion. Through the simple test-case discussed in subsection IV-A, heuristically we found that the

relation (18) allows for a stable calculation when the CFL coefficient is set equal to $K^* = 1.13$. Conversely, varying the K factor we found further regions of stability which can be generally indicated as:

$$K < f\left(\frac{c_{0X}}{c_{0Y}}, \eta\right) \quad \eta := \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_X \rho_{0Y}}{\gamma_Y \rho_{0X}}} < 1 \quad (19)$$

where f is a monotonically non-increasing function of the variables (c_{0X}/c_{0Y}) and η .

A. Numerical stability of the scheme through the Bagnold test

In order to derive the regions of stability given by the eq. (19) a 1-D Bagnold problem [3] has been considered. In particular, the same configuration adopted in [11] has been used for the test case: a liquid fluid patch is confined between two gas pockets under gravity forcing. In the initial condition the velocity is zero everywhere (see sketch in fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Sketch of the 1D Bagnold test. A patch of fluid X is confined by two gas pockets Y . At $t = 0$ the fluid velocity is zero and the fluid is subjected by the gravity force.

For all the simulations the following parameters have been used: for the liquid $\gamma_X = 7$, and for the gas $\gamma_Y = 1.4$, $\delta = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.07$, $\epsilon = 0.02$ for both the phases. This simple test case is used to study the conditions in which the scheme maintains stable. Several combinations of density ratios and speed of sound have been tested.

In Fig. 2 the stability region is studied in the plane $(c_{0Y}/c_{0X}, K)$. Three different ratios $\rho_{0X}/\rho_{0Y} = 10, 100, 1000$ have been considered which corresponds to three η values 0.71, 0.22, 0.071 (see eq. (19) and considering the ratio of the polytropic coefficients fixed to the value $\gamma_X/\gamma_Y = 5$). For this simple case the maximum K reached is $K_{max} = 1.4$ much higher than the 0.75 values used in SPH simulations discussed in section V. It is worth to note that in this 1D test case the advection of the particles is very small which is not the case for the other SPH simulations presented in the paper. The bullets dots in figure 2 represent the maximum K value to obtain a stable SPH simulation for a given couple $(c_{0Y}/c_{0X}, \eta)$. The unstable simulations, not shown here for the sake of brevity, appear as affected by numerical high frequencies pressure oscillation inside the two gas cavities with increasing amplitude in time.

In the simulations performed in the next section the ratio c_{0X}/c_{0Y} is always less than one, since we consider the X phase as a liquid and Y phase as a gas. As explained above, in such a condition, where c_{0Y} is higher than c_{0X} . The optimal condition $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} = \eta$, which allows to use the $K = K^*$, may not be adopted since the condition $c_{0X} = \eta c_{0Y}$ could not satisfy the weakly-compressible criterion (17). Therefore, in such a situation it is necessary to reduce the K parameter to adopt the right speed of sounds. As a consequence higher CPU costs are sometimes required.

In figure 3 the stability regions evaluated with the δ -SPH are compared with the ones given by the Riemann-SPH. The comparison shows that for the condition $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} = \eta$ the CFL number decreases to $K^+ = 0.62$ which is 1.8 lower than K^* . On the other hand, the limits given by Riemann-SPH presents a total different behaviour. Indeed, the CFL remains almost constant in the whole range of the ratio c_{0X}/c_{0Y} with just a small reduction of 0.1 when passing from

Fig. 2. Two-phase Bagnold problem: region of stability for the δ -SPH. Each bullets represent the maximum CFL number needed for a given density ratio ρ_{0X}/ρ_{0Y} and speed of sound ratio c_{0X}/c_{0Y} , X and Y being the heavier and lighter phase, respectively. The solid lines represent the regression lines delimiting the stability region for each η value, η being the parameter defined in formula (18). The yellow bullets in the graph represent the points where $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} = \eta$ and $K = K^*$.

Fig. 3. Two-phase Bagnold problem: comparison of the stability regions of the δ -SPH and of the Riemann-SPH. Each bullets represent the maximum CFL number needed for a given density ratio ρ_{0X}/ρ_{0Y} and speed of sound ratio c_{0X}/c_{0Y} , X and Y being the heavier and lighter phase, respectively. The yellow bullets in the graph represent the points where $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} = \eta$ and $K = K^*$ while the green bullets are the points where $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} = \eta$ and $K = K^+$.

$c_{0X}/c_{0Y} < 1$ to $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} > 1$. Thanks to this plot, when comparing the two SPH models, for a given density ratio ρ_{0X}/ρ_{0Y} , there are ratio of c_{0X}/c_{0Y} where Riemann-SPH can be more CPU demanding than the δ -SPH and vice-versa. For example, considering low density ratio $\rho_{0X}/\rho_{0Y} \leq 10$ the CFL for the δ -SPH is always greater than the Riemann-SPH one. This is not the case when increasing ρ_{0X}/ρ_{0Y} . For the air-water case, in the condition $c_{0X}/c_{0Y} > 0.15$, the Riemann-SPH remains stable with CFLs greater than the δ -SPH one.

The theoretical reasons of such kind of behaviours for those

stability constraints is still missing, for this reason this topic deserves a further investigation also in order to find possible solutions to go beyond those limits presented here.

V. FLUID IMPACT OF A CORRUGATED PANEL WITH TRAPPED GAS CAVITY

In order to test the ability of the proposed model to correctly compute the pressure in challenging problems such as the water impact, the problem of the water entry of a corrugated panel on a liquid free-surface with a trapped gas cavity is considered. Khabakhpasheva et al. (2013) provided a semi-analytical solution for this problem in [14] derived from the Wagner theory. In that work they studied the initial stage of an incompressible liquid impact onto both rigid and elastic corrugated panels, accounting for a compressible gas pocket trapped between the corrugations (see sketch in figure 4). The corrugation shape function is described by the following function:

$$f(x) = h \left[1 - \cos^4 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2\tilde{L}} \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

where h and $\tilde{L}$ are the corrugation's height and half-width respectively. This panel shape is noted in literature as Mark III panel which is a type of containment tank of Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) carriers (for more details see e.g. [18]).

The distance between the two corrugations is $2L$ (see Fig. 4) whereas the total panel length is $2c$. Similarly to [14] the following dimensions are adopted in all the simulations: $h = 3.6$ cm, $2\tilde{L} = 5.6$ cm and $2L = 34$ cm. At the initial time $t = 0$, the corrugations touch the free-surface at two points $x = \pm L$ and the fluids are at rest. The gas cavity is bounded by the panel and the free-surface and the panel penetrates the liquid surface with a purely vertical velocity U . In Khabakhpasheva et al. (2013) [14], the gas in the cavity is modelled adopting the polytropic state equation (8) discussed in section III-A. In that work the pressure inside the cavity is assumed as a function of the gas volume, which means that the pressure is considered homogeneous in the gas phase. The solution provided in [14] is general and valid for any density ratio between the liquid and the gas phase.

Since the focus is on high density ratios configurations, in the following test cases the water and air stand for the liquid and gas

Fig. 4. Sketch of the problem Fluid impact of a corrugated panel with trapped gas cavity corrugation panel.

Fig. 5. Left: Multi-resolution discretization of the domain. Right: Zoom on the gas cavity vicinity.

phases respectively, with a density ratio of 1000 and the polytropic coefficients are set to $\gamma_{air} = 1.4$ and $\gamma_{water} = 7$.

In order to correctly take into account the compressibility effects in the air cavity the same value used in [14] for the gas speed of sound is adopted, that is $c_{0air} = 343$ m/s. As for the water sound speed, formula (17) is used to guarantee the weakly-compressible hypothesis in the impact region, this being the common choice in SPH to approximate incompressible fluids. Based on the expected maximum pressure variation $\Delta P_{max} = 1$ atm in the cavity, the sound speed in water is obtained as

$$c_{0water} = 10 \sqrt{\Delta P_{max} / \rho_{water}} = 100 \text{ m/s.}$$

It results that $c_{0water}/c_{0air} \approx 0.29$. Note that, following the stability conditions described in section (IV), the CFL has been set equal to

Fig. 6. Pressure field during the impact stages for four different time instants $t^* = 0.014, 0.42, 0.55, 0.90$. The panel length is $c^* = 2$.

$K = 0.2$, with an artificial viscosity parameter $\alpha = 0.07$. In such a condition the Riemann-SPH model would be more efficient allowing a CFL number three times larger, i.e. $K = 0.60$. This comparison is left for future investigation on the topic.

In order to avoid the mixing of air and water, the artificial surface tension correction (13) is used, and the parameter ϵ_γ is set to 0.02. In the following, the dimensionless variables are denoted by the superscript *. The length L is taken as reference length scale of the problem, unless specified otherwise; U and h/U are chosen as, respectively, the velocity and time scales; the ratio $P_{0air} = c_{0air}^2 \rho_{0air} / \gamma_{air}$ is taken as the pressure reference scale in the gas cavity.

Two discretizations were tested, $L/\Delta x = 160, 640$. These values are based on the work of Marrone et al. [18], where the same type of corrugated panel was tested with a dead-rise angle of 4° , and in which these resolutions yielded satisfactory, convergent results. Note that the panel impact generates several acoustic waves which would be reflected off of the domain walls if the latter is not large enough, resulting in noisy pressure fields even in the air phase. Therefore, the domain is made sufficiently large and its dimensions were chosen simply by computing the distance which acoustic waves would travel during the impact at the adopted water sound speed. The variable- h scheme discussed in [22] was used since the focus is on the gas cavity and its vicinity. The particle size varies between the air cavity to the domain walls from fine to coarse respectively, with a magnification factor of 100 between the smallest and biggest resolutions. Since the problem is 2D symmetrical with respect to the line $x^* = 0$, a symmetry boundary condition was used.

As depicted in Fig. 6, the SPH solution can be viewed as a succession of 4 stages:

Stage 1) A compression of the gas up until $t^* = 0.45$ during which the pressure grows linearly akin to an elastic reaction, due to the homogeneous water load around it.

Stage 2) during the high speed water jet motion, the cavity is sucked towards the outside of the corrugation inducing a relaxation in the gas cavity during which the pressure keeps decreasing.

Stage 3) After the jet reaches the end of the panel, the suction effect becomes dialled down and is counterbalanced by the water pressure from under the gas cavity. Therefore, as the panel continues to penetrate the water, the cavity resumes its compression in this stage.

Stage 4) Around $t^* = 0.85$, the pressure reaches its second peak then the gas cavity begins its decompression as the loads balance out during this final stage.

Fig. 7 shows the δ -SPH time history of the pressure inside the cavity compared against the semi-analytical solution derived in [14]. The δ -SPH results are obtained with two resolutions: coarse ($L/dx = 160$) and fine ($L/dx = 640$).

There are some differences between the SPH and semi-analytical curves which are limited and reflect the different natures of the solutions being compared. In fact, in Khabakhpasheva et al. [14] the air cavity was prevented from reaching the head of the corrugation by imposing the condition that gas pocket will remain confined within the corrugation. With this constraint the horizontal velocity of the inner contact point always points towards the center of the cavity, which means that the air will never flow under the corrugation. In the present simulations however, no condition on the inner contact point's velocity is enforced, so that the cavity is left to freely evolve in time.

Next, the effect of the panel length on the cavity pressure is investigated. The numerical and geometrical configurations are kept unchanged, however this time the panel length is $c^* = 3$. The simulation was run with the fine discretization ratio $L/\Delta x = 640$. Fig. 8 compares the evolutions of the cavity pressures for both panel lengths $c^* = 2$ and $c^* = 3$. Fig. 8 regroups the semi-analytical and

Fig. 7. Comparison with the semi-analytical solution of the pressure inside the cavity, for a panel length $c^* = 2$. The pressure curve is divided into 4 stages.

computed pressure solutions for both panel lengths $c^* = 2$ and 3, from which some general conclusions can be made. First, in accordance with [14], the shorter the panel, the lower the pressure inside the cavity. Also, right away it can be seen that both pressure curves follow the same general trend, in the sense that they both predict the aforementioned 4 phases. The curves are superposed during Phases 1 and 2 which is expected since the water does not reach c^* yet. The solution with the larger panel agrees the conclusions made for the shorter panel, meaning that the SPH pressure follows closely the semi-analytical one in terms of compression + relaxation in Phase 3 and 4, albeit at different pressure levels since the air cavity is not constrained within the SPH model, while it is set to move only towards the inside within the semi-analytical model.

Fig. 8. Semi-analytical and computed pressure profiles in the cavity, for panel lengths of $c^* = 2$ and 3.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a multi-fluid weakly-compressible SPH model in which the δ -SPH diffusive terms were extended to multi-phase flow, and adapted to the volumes equation of the Grenier et al. model [9, 10] in order to eliminate the spurious oscillations of pressure. As the Riemann-SPH model of [15], the proposed model handles the presence of a free-surface in addition to the fluids interface.

The time stepping and the choice of the speeds of sound for the different phases were discussed, highlighting how this choice is driven by physical consideration and numerical constraints linked to the stability of the scheme. Concerning the latter, it was shown that the two SPH variants, δ - and Riemann- SPH, have different regions of stability when a multi-phase flow is considered. For some density

and speed of sound ratios the δ -SPH model allows for bigger time steps, but in other conditions the contrary holds.

As a testing problem, a challenging test case was studied in which the presence of a free-surface is combined with the presence of an entrapped air cavity generating a complex water impact flow. It involved the water entry of corrugated MarkIII panel. The corrugations are small rigid structures under the flat panel, and their shape is given by an analytical function. The SPH results were compared with a semi-analytical approach based on the Wagner condition. As expected, the pressure field was found to be quasi-homogeneous inside the air cavity. However, the Wagner condition was found to greatly impact the cavity volume evolution since it behaves quite differently if the inner contact point is left to move freely. Nevertheless, despite the restrictions of the Wagner condition, both the SPH and semi-analytical solutions can be considered to be in satisfactory agreement.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The proposed SPH multi-phase model will be used in the context of violent sloshing wing dynamics within the framework of the SLOWD project (which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815044).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Antuono, A. Colagrossi, and S. Marrone. Numerical diffusive terms in weakly-compressible SPH schemes. *Computer Physics Communications*, 183(12):2570 – 2580, 2012.
- [2] M. Antuono, A. Colagrossi, S. Marrone, and D. Molteni. Free-surface flows solved by means of SPH schemes with numerical diffusive terms. *Computer Physics Communications*, 181(3):532 – 549, 2010.
- [3] R.A. Bagnold. Interim report on wave-pressure research. *Excerpt from the J. of the Institution of Civil Engineers*, 1939.
- [4] A. Colagrossi, M. Antuono, and D. Le Touzé. Theoretical considerations on the free-surface role in the smoothed-particle-hydrodynamics model. *Phys. Rev. E*, 79:056701, May 2009.
- [5] A. Colagrossi, B. Bouscasse, M. Antuono, and S. Marrone. Particle packing algorithm for SPH schemes. *Computer Physics Communications*, 183(2):1641–1683, 2012.
- [6] A. Colagrossi and M. Landrini. Numerical simulation of interfacial flows by smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *J. Comput. Phys.*, 191(2):448–475, November 2003.
- [7] Pep Español and Mariano Revenga. Smoothed dissipative particle dynamics. *Phys. Rev. E*, 67:026705, Feb 2003.
- [8] T.P. Fries and H.G. Matthies. Classification and Overview of Meshfree Methods. *Scientific Computing, Informatikbericht*, 2004.
- [9] N. Grenier, M. Antuono, A. Colagrossi, D. Le Touzé, and B. Alessandrini. An hamiltonian interface SPH formulation for multi-fluid and free surface flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 228(22):8380 – 8393, 2009.
- [10] N. Grenier, David Le Touzé, A. Colagrossi, M. Antuono, and G. Colicchio. Viscous bubbly flows simulation with an interface sph model. *Ocean Engineering*, 69:88 – 102, 2013.
- [11] P.M. Guilcher, G. Oger, E. Jacquin, L. Brosset, N. Grenier, D. Le Touzé, et al. Simulation of liquid impacts with a two-phase parallel SPH model. In *The Twentieth International Offshore and Polar Engineering Conference*. International Society of Offshore and Polar Engineers, 2010.
- [12] X.Y. Hu and N.A. Adams. A multi-phase sph method for macroscopic and mesoscopic flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 213(2):844 – 861, 2006.
- [13] M. J. Ivings, D. M. Causon, and E. F. Toro. On riemann solvers for compressible liquids. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids*, 28(3):395–418, 1998.
- [14] T.I. Khabakhpasheva, A.A. Korobkin, and S. Malenica. Fluid impact onto a corrugated panel with trapped gas cavity. *Applied Ocean Research*, 39:97 – 112, 2013.
- [15] J. Leduc, F. Leboeuf, M. Lance, E. Parkinson, and J.C. Marongiu. A sph-ale method to model multiphase flows with surface tension. In *Proceeding 7th international conference on multiphase flow, Tampa*, 2010.
- [16] S. Marrone, M. Antuono, A. Colagrossi, G. Colicchio, D. Le Touzé, and G. Graziani. δ -SPH model for simulating violent impact flows. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 200(13):1526 – 1542, 2011.
- [17] S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, A. Di Mascio, and D. Le Touzé. Prediction of energy losses in water impacts using incompressible and weakly compressible models. *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, 54:802–822, 2015.
- [18] S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, J.S. Park, and E.F. Campana. Challenges on the numerical prediction of slamming loads on lng tank insulation panels. *Ocean Engineering*, 141:512 – 530, 2017.
- [19] J.J. Monaghan. Simulating Free Surface Flows with SPH. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 110(2):39–406, 1994.
- [20] A. Murrone and H. Guillard. A five equation reduced model for compressible two phase flow problems. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 202(2):664 – 698, 2005.
- [21] S. Nugent and H.A. Posch. Liquid drops and surface tension with smoothed particle applied mechanics. *Physical Review E*, 62(4):4968, 2000.
- [22] G. Oger, M. Doring, B. Alessandrini, and P. Ferrant. Two-dimensional sph simulations of wedge water entries. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 213(2):803 – 822, 2006.
- [23] S. Osher. Riemann solvers, the entropy condition, and difference. *SIAM Journal on Numerical Analysis*, 21(2):217–235, 1984.
- [24] A.N. Parshikov and S.A. Medin. Smoothed particle hydrodynamics using interparticle contact algorithms. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 180(1):358 – 382, 2002.
- [25] K. Szewc, J. Pozorski, and J.P. Minier. Spurious interface fragmentation in multiphase sph. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 103(9):625–649, 2015.
- [26] Bram van Leer. Towards the ultimate conservative difference scheme. v. a second-order sequel to godunov's method. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 32(1):101 – 136, 1979.
- [27] J.P. Vila. On particle weighted methods and smooth particle hydrodynamics. *Mathematical models and methods in applied sciences*, 9(02):161–209, 1999.
- [28] H. Wendland. Piecewise polynomial, positive definite and compactly supported radial functions of minimal degree. *Advances in computational Mathematics*, 4(1):389–396, 1995.